

Capturing Basic Semantic Relationships between Objects

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Jochen Triesch and Arthur Aubret

Our third work package within the ARENA project aims to investigate whether SLTT learning leads to object representations that capture the semantic relationship between objects. Humans tend to judge more similar objects that belong to the same context; for instance, a knife is semantically similar to a teapot because they both frequently occur within a kitchen context.

In a first work by Aubret et al. (2024), we simulated toddlers learning in a complex environment composed of several contexts. Objects predictably show up in certain contexts (e.g. a toothbrush in a bathroom) and the toddler model spends a certain time in one context before transitioning to another (e.g., going from the bathroom to the kitchen). Interestingly, we show that in the highest layers of the neural network, very abstract concepts such as “bathroom object” or “kitchen object” develop, while lower layers excel at representing object class (e.g. chair) or identity of a particular object instance (my office chair).

This first work uses hand-crafted context-transitions and curated video clips of objects. In Schaumlöffel et al. (2025), we trained our SLTT model on 3,600 hours of videos derived from head-mounted cameras and simulated gaze positions. This data captures natural object and context transitions faced by humans. Our results show that SLTT learns object representations that are more similar for pairs of objects that co-occur in natural scenes.

In summary, our research clearly indicates that the biological principle of temporal slowness may explain the context-wise semantic similarity judgements made by humans. In future work, we plan to collaborate with the group of Prof. Melissa Vo to compare the development of semantic object representations in humans and our models in a controlled fashion. Both humans and models will be exposed to the same interactions recorded within an environment composed of novel objects. This will validate our conclusions while reducing the differences between the training experiences of the model and humans.

Aubret, A., Schaumlöffel, T., Roig, G., & Triesch, J. (2024). Learning Object Semantic Similarity with Self-Supervision. Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Development and Learning (ICDL). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.05143>

*Schaumlöffel, T., *Aubret, A., Roig, G., & Triesch, J. (2025). Temporal Slowness in Central Vision Drives Semantic Object Learning. Submitted for publication.